

AN ANALYSIS OF THE JAPANESE EDUCATION SYSTEM: STRUCTURE, MORAL INSTRUCTION, AND LEARNING OUTCOMES

Samandarova Gulsanam Ilhom qizi

Student of the Faculty of English Philology,
Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Email: gulsanamsamandarova9@gmail.com

Supervisor: **Yazdonova Makhfuza Alisher qizi**

Abstract: This article examines the key features of Japan's education system and their impact on student development and academic achievement. The aim of the study is to identify the main factors that contribute to the effectiveness of this system. The research is based on a descriptive and qualitative analysis of secondary sources, including international reports and previous studies. The findings suggest that Japan's success in education is closely related to its structured system, strong discipline, and effective teaching methods. In addition, moral education and responsibility-based practices play an important role in shaping students' behavior. As a result, students not only achieve high academic results but also develop important social skills. The study concludes that certain elements of Japan's education system can be applied in other countries to improve educational outcomes.

Key words: Japanese education system, effectiveness, discipline, moral education, high academic results, responsibility, compulsory education

Introduction: Education is one of the most important factors influencing the development of modern societies. Many countries today face challenges such as declining student motivation, weak discipline, and unsatisfactory academic results. These issues make it necessary to study successful education systems and identify effective practices. Japan is often considered one of the countries with a highly effective education system. Its students consistently perform well in international assessments, and it is well-known for focusing not only on academic knowledge but also on character development. Japanese education system create an environment where students can learn to work together, respect others, and take responsibility for their actions. The aim of this article is to analyze the main features of Japan's education system, including its structure, discipline, teaching methods, and learning outcomes, and to explain how these elements contribute to student success.

Main body:

Key features and structure of it: Japanese education system is widely regarded as one of the most effective one in the world. It follows a 6+3+3+4 structure, which includes six years of primary education, three years of lower secondary education, three years of upper secondary education, four years of university. The first nine years are compulsory. It consists of:

✓ Early Childhood Education – Yōchien (Ages 3–6)

Although early childhood education in Japan is not compulsory, the majority of children attend kindergarten. This stage is primarily aimed at helping children adapt to group environments and preparing them for formal schooling. The curriculum focuses on developing independence, understanding social rules, and improving basic language and motor skills through activities such as music, drawing, and structured play. Rather than formal testing, emphasis is placed on gradual development and social interaction^[4]. This approach helps children build essential communication skills and emotional awareness at an early age, which positively influences their future learning behavior.

✓ Primary Education – Shōgakkō (Ages 6–12)

Primary education lasts six years and is both compulsory and free of charge. During this stage, students study core subjects such as Japanese, mathematics, science, and social studies, along with arts, music, and physical education. Moral education is also integrated into the curriculum, promoting ethical values and cooperative behavior. In addition, foreign language learning, typically English, is gradually introduced. Student progress is assessed through continuous evaluation rather than high-stakes final examinations^[4]. This system reduces academic pressure while encouraging consistent learning, which leads to a more stable and supportive educational environment. Furthermore, discipline, organization, and respect are emphasized in daily school life, resulting in the development of responsible and self-disciplined individuals.

✓ Lower Secondary Education – Chūgakkō (Ages 12–15)

Lower secondary education is also compulsory and builds upon the foundation established in primary school. The curriculum includes more advanced study in core academic subjects, as well as foreign languages, technology, and civic education. At this stage, students begin preparing for competitive high school entrance examinations^[4]. This early preparation increases students' academic focus and motivation, although it may also introduce a higher level of pressure. Nevertheless, it plays a crucial role in shaping students' future educational pathways.

✓ Upper Secondary Education – Kōkō (Ages 15–18)

Although upper secondary education is not mandatory, the vast majority of students continue their studies at this level. Admission is based on entrance examinations, making this stage highly competitive. Schools offer different academic tracks, including general programs for university preparation and vocational pathways for direct entry into the workforce. Due to the competitive nature of university admissions, many students attend additional preparatory classes outside regular school hours^[4]. This reflects the strong emphasis placed on academic achievement and future career success in Japanese society.

✓ Higher Education

Higher education in Japan is characterized by its selectivity and academic rigor. Admission to universities is largely determined by entrance examinations, which require thorough preparation. University programs typically include undergraduate degrees lasting three to four years, followed by master's and doctoral studies^[4]. This structured and competitive system ensures high academic standards, although it also requires significant effort and dedication from students.

Academic Calendar: In principle, the school year begins in April and ends in March of the following year. Most schools adopt a three-semester system, with the first semester from April to August, the second semester from September to December, and the third semester from January to March. There is also a summer break (from the end of July to the end of August), a winter break (from the end of December to the beginning of January), and a spring break (from the end of March to the beginning of April)^[3].

Daily School Schedule: In Japanese elementary schools, the school week usually runs from Monday to Friday. Students typically arrive at school between 8:00 and 8:20 in the morning. The day begins with a short morning assembly, which takes place around 8:25 to 8:35, where teachers take attendance and make important announcements. The first lesson starts at approximately 8:45, and each class lasts about 45 minutes. Short breaks of 5 to 10 minutes are given between lessons, while a slightly longer break of around 20 minutes usually occurs after the second period. Most students have four lessons in the morning before lunchtime, which is generally around midday. After lunch and a short rest period, students usually attend one or two additional classes. In total, a normal school day consists of about five to six periods, ending either around 2:30 pm or 3:30 pm depending on the schedule. Younger students often have a shorter day with four to five lessons, while older elementary students (especially 5th and 6th graders) typically follow a full six-period schedule^[2].

Moral education: discipline, responsibility. While many education systems prioritize academic achievement, Japan places equal importance on moral education. Japanese schools aim to develop student's character, discipline, and sense of social responsibility alongside academic knowledge. This balanced approach has contributed to the formation of a highly disciplined, respectful, and cooperative student culture. In Japan, moral education is not taught as a separate subject but is integrated into everyday school life. Students learn responsibility through practical activities, discipline through structured routines, and respect through behavior rather than punishment. One of the most distinctive practices is that students are responsible for cleaning their classrooms and school facilities. This activity promotes teamwork, equality, and a sense of ownership over shared spaces. Moreover, discipline in Japanese schools is based on mutual respect and clear expectations rather than strict punishment, which helps students develop self-control and emotional awareness. Group work is also a central element of school life. Through collaborative learning and shared responsibilities, students develop communication skills, empathy, and leadership qualities. Teachers play a key role in this process by acting as mentors and guiding student's behavior and social interactions^[1]. Overall, moral education in Japan supports both personal and academic development. By fostering discipline, cooperation, and emotional intelligence, it creates an environment where students can succeed both in school and in society.

Trained teachers: Teachers in Japan are well-trained, which provides a strong foundation for the education of students. Teacher training involves planning that helps teachers learn from each other and improve their teaching methods. Teachers are highly respected in Japan^[7]. This high level of professional preparation ensures consistency in teaching quality and allows educators to apply effective instructional strategies in the classroom. As a result, students benefit from a more structured and supportive learning environment.

Relationship between teachers and students: There is a strong connection between teachers and students in Japan. The relationship between teachers and students is deeply rooted in a hierarchical structure and strong emphasis on respect, often characterized by a "kyoushokuin" (teacher) role that extends beyond instruction to encompass guidance and mentorship. This relationship fosters a positive learning environment, with many teachers prioritizing the influence on students' development and contribution to society. Studies suggest that these positive teacher-student relationships promote

student motivation, engagement, and academic achievement^[7]. This close interaction not only strengthens classroom discipline but also enhances students' emotional development and sense of responsibility. It can be argued that such relationships play a key role in creating a collaborative and effective educational atmosphere.

Learning outcomes in Japan: Japan consistently performs well on major international education assessments, including the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS). Japan has ranked among the top performers on both PISA and TIMSS since 2000, particularly in mathematics, and its scores have been highly equitable. On the 2022 PISA, for example, only 12 percent of Japanese students were low performers in math, compared to the OECD average of 31 percent, and the overall impact of socio-economic status on student performance in that subject was also measured at 12 percent, below the OECD average of 15 percent. Scores in Japan also tend to show low levels of variance in performance across schools^[5]. This strong and consistent performance indicates that Japan's education system not only achieves high academic results but also ensures equality among students. As a result, the gap between high- and low-performing students remains relatively small, which reflects the effectiveness of structured teaching methods and equal learning opportunities.

Unlike many countries, Japanese higher education does not have a standardized grading system. However, most universities use a four-point scale of A, B, C, and F. Only the most exceptional work is graded A, and F is considered failing. Students who receive the latter can retake the exam or assignment^[6]. This grading approach places emphasis on quality and mastery rather than competition. It can be argued that such a system encourages students to focus on deeper understanding and continuous improvement instead of simply achieving high grades.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, Japan's education system stands out as a well-balanced and effective model that combines academic excellence with strong moral and social development. The structured organization of the system, together with the emphasis on moral education, plays a crucial role in shaping disciplined, responsible, and cooperative individuals. Furthermore, the role of teachers as both educators and mentors, along with the use of student-centered teaching methods, contributes significantly to creating an engaging and supportive learning environment. These approaches encourage active participation, critical thinking, and continuous improvement among students. The

consistently high performance of Japanese students in international assessments such as PISA and TIMSS demonstrates the effectiveness of this system. At the same time, the focus on equality and low variation in student outcomes highlights its ability to provide quality education for all learners.

Overall, Japan's education system offers valuable insights for other countries. It can be argued that integrating moral education, effective teaching strategies, and structured learning environments can lead to both academic success and the development of well-rounded individuals.

References:

1. Dolphin Public School: Japan's Moral Education System: Building Discipline, Responsibility & Teamwork in Schools. Retrieved: February 5, 2026. From: <https://dolphinpublicschool.org/japans-moral-education-system-building-discipline-responsibility-teamwork-in-schools/>
2. E-housing: School Time in Japan: Daily schedule, Lunch, and After-School Care. Retrieved: October 29, 2025. From: <https://e-housing.jp/post/elementary-school-time-in-japan-daily-schedule-lunch-and-after-school-care>
3. JAPAN Educational Travel: JAPANESE EDUCATION SYSTEM. From: <https://education.jnto.go.jp/en/school-in-japan/japanese-education-system/>
4. International Schools Brussels: Japanese Education System in Brussels International Schools. From: <https://internationalschools.brussels/en/japanese-education-system-curriculum-and-diploma/>
5. NCEE: Japan + NCEE. From: <https://ncee.org/japan/>
6. Mamatkarimov K. Z: Japanese Education System And Assessment Standards: From: <https://scientists.uz/fileView.php?id=7264>
7. ResearchGate: Japanese Education system: From: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/391229871_Japanese_Education_System